

Ultrafast Dynamics at 25T in Photosynthetic Protein Complexes

M. Maiuri¹, M. B. Oviedo^{1,2}, J. C. Dean¹, Z. S. D. Toa¹, M. Bishop³,
Bryan M. Wong², S. McGill³, G.D. Scholes¹

¹*Department of Chemistry, Princeton University, Washington Road, Princeton, 08544, New Jersey, United States.*

²*Department of Chemical & Environmental Engineering and Materials Science & Engineering Program, University of California-Riverside, Riverside, California 92521, United States.*

³*National High Magnetic Field Laboratory (NHFML), Paul Dirac Dr. 1800, Tallahassee, Florida, United States.
E-mail: mmaiuri@princeton.edu*

Abstract: Ultrafast coherences in photosynthetic algae proteins are discriminated by using 25T-magnetic field coupled with a pump-probe apparatus. Electronic/vibronic coherences are modulated by the presence of the field, while vibrations are not perturbed.

OCIS codes: (300.6530) Spectroscopy, ultrafast; (300.6240) Spectroscopy, coherent transient.

Nature has developed sophisticated ways to control photosynthetic complexes where the arrangement of the individual pigments in specific configurations set by the protein scaffold is finely engineered to funnel the absorbed energy and transfer it to reaction centers via electronic energy transfer (EET) with evolutionary efficiency (> 95%) [1].

In the last decade it has been discovered that light-harvesting (LH) in Nature may involve quantum-coherence [2]. At the basis of the most interesting coherence effects in LH systems are molecular excitons which can be seen as electronic excited states where the wavefunction is shared by two or more molecules. This coherent superposition of states evolves in time and can be observed by spectral features that are perturbed, shifted, or split. The observation of long-lived electronic coherence in some photosynthetic complexes at cryogenic and ambient temperatures [2-4], has generated deep interest in the role of quantum mechanical effects in EET. This discovery has tremendous implications for the formulation of EET theories and consequently, it will affect the way we should think about energy transfer mechanisms and how artificial LH systems should be designed [5].

Traditionally, EET in LH complexes has been treated directly with Förster theory where the excitation “hops” from one site to another incoherently [6]. However the inclusion of quantum coherence calls for a scenario where the involved chromophores are strongly coupled (compared with coupling to the bath) and the donor/acceptor electronic states become mixed, thus delocalizing the excitation [7]. Furthermore “vibronic” coupling has been recently highlighted to describe the influence of the Franck-Condon active vibrations on coherence [7].

Spectrally resolved pump-probe spectroscopy (SRPP) and two-dimensional electronic spectroscopy (2DES) are techniques which are highly sensitive to population and coherent dynamics in time-resolved transient signals, and allow effective spectral identification and assignment of the active electronic/vibronic bands emitting the coherent signal [7,8]. Coherences are identified in these experiments as oscillating signals with a characteristic period that reports on the energy difference between the two levels involved in the superposition, and their spectral position further aids in identifying those specific levels/chromophores involved. One of the main open questions arising from these experiments involves the nature of the observed coherences and what role they play.

Here we propose a new approach to address the problem of disentangling electronic/vibronic coherences by envisaging that a strong magnetic field will serve as the non-invasive reagent needed to modify the excitonic nature of the chromophores in the proteins, thereby affecting only the excitonic levels while not perturbing significantly the vibrational structure. We foresee that by comparing coherent temporal dynamics measured via broadband SRPP in a high magnetic field and in the absence of the magnetic field, we will be capable of discriminating between electronic/ vibronic coherence, offering a new powerful way to solve a major topic of debate in the community at present.

A tailored spectrally-resolved pump-probe apparatus (SRPP) was implemented at the Split Florida-Helix facility at the National High Magnetic Field Laboratory (NHMFL, Figure 1a), pumped by a home-built NOPA delivering broadband pulses in the visible frequency range compressed down to 25-fs. Short pulses enabled us to excite and detect coherent oscillations in the time domain. By a post-process Fourier analysis of the pump-probe data, we frequency-resolved the modes forming coherent signals and compared the results in absence/presence (0/25T) of the external field. We tested the sensitivity of our system on a reference dye (cresyl violet) and found that the fundamental vibrational mode of the dye [9] is clearly observed at 0T and 25T, proving no effect of magnetic field on non-excitonic systems (Figure 1b).

Fig. 1. (a) SRPP apparatus built at NHFML. (b) Left: $\Delta T/T$ Pump-Probe map of Cresyl Violet (inset) at 25T; right: single FT trace at 500 THz probe frequency at 25T (red) compared with the same FT traces obtained at 0T (Pump-probe map at 0T here not reported). The FT traces have been calculated by Fourier transforming residual oscillations obtained after subtraction of bi-exponential fit of the pump-probe traces.

We measured coherent dynamics occurring in two phycobiliproteins (PBPs), which are contained in the thylakoid lumen of Cryptophyte algae and exhibit different structure and chromophore arrangements, as revealed by incoming crystallographic data. The open PC577 form and closed PC645 from *Hemiselmis pacifica* (CCMP 706) and *Chroomonas mesostigmatica* (CCMP 269) respectively are shown in Figure 2a.

It is reported that the EET mechanisms between these two types are different: PC645 exhibits signatures of electronic coherence observed by 2DES [10], while only vibrational coherences have been observed for PC577 hitherto [8]. Additionally, the close proximity of the central dihydrobiliverdin (DBV) pair in PC645 yields formation of excitonically coupled states, denoted DBV^+ and DBV^- , which splits and mixes the two zeroth-order states and establishes an initial ultrafast energy funnel from DBV^+ to DBV^- . DBV^- then exhibits weaker excitonic interactions with other nearby chromophores, giving rise to electronic coherence in spectroscopic studies. The DBV pair is responsible of initiating the EET towards the lowest pigments acceptors, named phycocyanobilins (PCB).

Fig. 2. Linear absorption and crystal structure of PC645 (a-b) and PC577 (c-d) respectively; (e)-(f): $\Delta T/T$ pump-probe map of PC645 and PC577 at 25T; (g)-(h) Fourier transform integrated power spectra at 25T (red) and 0T (black) (pump-probe map at 0T not shown here).

Fig.2 shows the pump probe maps of PC645 and PC577 at 0T and 25T and the corresponding FT spectra at selected probe frequency. For both the proteins, the 0T field experiment matches the coherence frequencies measured previously in Scholes's group [8,10]. In the PC645 protein, we observe - within the experimental noise- a frequency shift for the 1582 cm^{-1} mode at 25T (fig. 2g). The 1580 cm^{-1} mode is assigned to a raman active stretching mode of the acceptor PCB by previous resonant Raman experiments (11). In the PC577 protein, the frequency positions of the measured coherences seem to be less sensitive to the effect of the 25T field, following the hypothesis that the vibrational coherences will not be perturbed by the magnetic field.

In order to evaluate and quantify the interaction between a static magnetic field with a molecular exciton, we model the effect of the magnetic field for the PC645 protein using real-time TDDFT (12). We calculated

the effect of a 25T magnetic field on the excitonic coupling of the PC645 DBV central dimer where the chromophores are located 15.6 Å from each other (center-to-center distance). The calculated electronic excitation energies of either the DBV monomer and dimer found at 0T are slightly red shifted when the 25T magnetic field is active, leading to an increase of about 40 cm⁻¹ in the evaluation of the electronic coupling (13). This effect is the result of the modification of the electronic excitation energies and oscillator strength by the interaction of the magnetic moments with the static magnetic field through the Zeeman effect. The perturbation of the excitonic resonances of the DBV chromophore pair induced by the magnetic field is observable through our broadband pump-probe experiment as the shift of the coherent peak in the integrated Fourier power spectrum in the high frequency region. We propose that the strong coherence at 1580 cm⁻¹ exhibits a vibronic character: a mixture of vibrational and electronic, shared between the donor DBVs and the acceptor PCB. The PCB vibration is indeed in resonance with the electronic energy gap between the DBV electronic excited state and the lowest PCB zero-order electronic excited level. The magnetic field interacts primarily with the DBVs electronic coupling by increasing the excitonic splitting: tuning this energetic gap sub-sequentially changes the strength of the vibronic interaction with the acceptor PCB vibrational levels because the DBV states is pushed further out of resonances. This is reflected in a spectral shift of the vibronic frequency at 25T.

By combining ultra-high magnetic fields and coherent broadband spectroscopy, our experiment offers a different approach to disentangle vibrational/electronic contribution among different chromophores involved in light harvesting complexes, thanks to the explicit action of the magnetic field on the electronic resonances, while leaving the vibrational response unaffected.

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